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Teachers' Enneagram Personality Types, Their Perceived Organizational Culture and Mediation Attitudes*

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between teachers' enneagram personality types, their perceived organizational culture and mediation attitudes. Structural equation modeling is used in the study. The sample of the study consists of 463 teachers who work at primary, secondary and high school levels in public schools in Istanbul, Turkey. Enneagram Personality Scale, School Culture Scale, and Mediation Attitude Scale are used in the study. According to the results of the study, there are significant relationships between teachers' enneagram personality types, mediation attitudes, and organizational culture. Also, among the teachers' personality types Type 9, Type 8 and Type 1 predict teachers' mediation attitudes and organizational culture has a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' personality types and mediation attitudes. Therefore, personality types and the culture of the school should not be ignored for teachers to be able to mediate and to be guided to mediate.

Keywords: Enneagram, Organizational Culture, Mediation

1. Introduction

1.1 Introducing the Problem

People have come together and formed organizations to achieve some common goals and schools are one of the most crucial organizational structures for countries. Schools aim to educate the young generations who will be the future leaders, but rapid social change and educational reforms have driven schools to big transformations (Renihan et al., 2006, p. 13). During these transformations, there can be some conflicts or disputes between teachers. These disputes can be solved via mediation and to solve these disputes we see two things important, which are personality and organizational culture. Since conflicts are inevitable in schools, as in any organization,

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solutions should be found to deal with the negative effects of conflict. Hostile relationships are not productive in a school environment and schools should help their staff and students to develop conflict management skills. Alternative dispute resolution is a form of problem solving in which all parties participate to deal with conflict and find mutually acceptable solutions (Turan & Taylor, 1997, p. 8).

The culture of the organization, the conflicts experienced and the way these conflicts are managed affect the efficient operation of the organization. In addition, the attitudes, behaviours and approaches of other members of the school culture towards these conflicts are important in managing conflicts (Özmen & Aküzüm, 2010). Mediation is mostly used as peer mediation among students in schools, but mediation can also be useful for the conflicts between teachers and between teachers and administrators (Turan & Taylor, 1997, p. 9). Because conflicts are a part of schools, these can be sometimes between teachers (Sucuoğlu, 2015; VADR, 2001; Yaraş & Gündüzalp, 2021; Zembat, 2012). School administrators are primarily responsible for managing and reconciling them. However, teachers, who are at the center of conflicts, can also be trained on the skills necessary to resolve these conflicts (Yaraş & Gündüzalp, 2021, p. 427). Also, since there are different personality types within organizations, their methods of dealing with conflicts will also be different (Magnuson, 2011). Considering Enneagram personality types, some types will deal with these conflicts better. For instance, Type 9s are excellent mediators, but Type 3s like to fight (McPartlin, 2021, p. 158). Therefore, it is seen that some types can choose mediation and be good mediator, but some can't.

There are some studies related to enneagram (Aktürk & Taştan, 2020; Schewee, 2023; Subaş, 2017; Şahin, 2019). Also, there are a lot of studies related to organizational culture in relationship with various aspects (Ayık & Ada, 2009; Clear, 2005; Özmen & Aküzüm, 2010; Sarı & Helvacı, 2019; Singh, 2007). Mediation is mostly studied as peer mediation between students or mediation skills of administrators in schools (Dağlı, 2013; Güloğlu, 2011) and there are limited studies related to teachers view about mediation, not their mediation attitudes (Şener, 2006). We couldn't find any studies which examine the relationship between mediation, organizational culture and enneagram. In this study, mediation is studied in terms of teachers. Two factors are considered important in mediating conflicts. One of these is the personality types of teachers and the other is organizational culture. The personality type of the teacher is important in whether he/she has mediation characteristics or not and whether he/she can carry out this intervention or not. In addition, the organizational culture of the institution, the prevailing situation in the institution can also affect whether teachers will make such an intervention or not. For this reason, in this study it is aimed to examine the relationship between teachers' enneagram personality types, their perceived organizational culture and mediation attitudes. In this direction, the sub-purposes are as follows:

1. Do teachers' enneagram personality types significantly predict teachers' mediation attitudes?
2. Do teachers' enneagram personality types significantly predict their perceptions of organizational culture?
3. Do teachers' perceptions of organizational culture significantly predict teachers' mediation attitudes?
4. Is there a mediating role of organizational culture in the relationship between teachers' enneagram personality types and mediation attitudes?

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Organizational Culture

In schools, there has always been a unique, powerful, yet challenging to define aspect that is felt by everyone. For this concept, we use the term "culture" which provides school leaders with a more accurate way to understand the unwritten rules, traditions, customs, and expectations of schools. These informal patterns influence everything from behaviour, relations to feelings (Deal & Peterson, 2016, p. 7). Schein (2004, p. 17) defined organizational culture as "a set of basic shared assumptions that the group has learned while resolving its problems of external adaptation and internal integration, that has worked well enough to be considered valid, and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems." Additionally, researchers have classified types of organizational culture in different ways (e.g., Handy, 1976; Harrison, 1972; Pheysy, 2003; Cameron & Quinn, 2006; Miles & Snow, 2003; Denison & Spreitzer, 1991).

Inspired by the earlier works of Harrison and Handy, Pheyse (2003) introduced four organizational culture types. In role culture, meeting expectations is crucial and government systems and large corporations can be given as examples. The term role specifies job descriptions, rules, and behavioral patterns related to how individuals in each position should act. In success culture, getting the job done is more important than the rules. Everybody is interested in their jobs and getting the job done is also important for their personal interests. Consulting firms, research organizations are examples of this type. It is the result of the interaction of people who have come together to solve their problems. In power culture, some people are more dominant and the rest just obey. Obedience to authority is dominant and there is a stable order with demarcated boundaries. In support culture, where personal relationships are important, bureaucracy is disliked and employees have the right to have a say in the decision-making system (Pheyse, 2003, pp. 15-18).

School culture is the traditions, values and beliefs that are unique to that school and established within its own history. Culture shows the ways things are done in a school (Kruse and Louis, 2008, p. 3). Schools are different from each other is because of the different cultures that have settled in schools over time. In order for schools to be effective, educators need to understand the dominant organizational culture in their schools (Gruenert & Whitaker, 2015, pp. 2-3). Also, school culture has a relationship with many issues such as school effectiveness (Ayık & Ada, 2009), student achievement (Clear, 2005; Demirtaş, 2010), teacher behaviours (Arpaguş, 2011), readiness for organizational change (Sarı & Helvacı, 2019), organizational commitment (Erkmen & Bozkurt, 2011; Singh, 2007), organizational citizenship (Kaya, 2015), perspectives or solutions to conflicts (Himmetoğlu, 2014; Özmen & Aküzüm, 2010). Therefore, the importance of organizational culture, which affects everything in schools so much, should not be underestimated and should be included in the studies.

1.2.2 Enneagram

Personality consists of innate and learned abilities and skills, environment, education, instincts and ambitions, situations, the influence of others and personality type. Although many of these factors change, the personality type remains the same throughout a person's life. Knowing the personality types of the people they work with helps managers to understand what motivates them, what they like to do, what they are predisposed to, how they will behave in certain situations, how they will perform a task, why some people have conflicts with others or with themselves (Garner, 2012, pp. 11-12). Therefore, it is important to know the personality types of the employees in the organization for the sake of the leader and organizational culture. One of the best models for determining personality types and understanding oneself is Enneagram (Ferda & Karabulut, 2004, s. 7). Enneagram describes nine personality types, their patterns and the subconscious motives behind these patterns (Makani, 2010, p. 11).

Type 1s are called the Enneagram's perfectionists. They set high standards for themselves. They have high moral standards. They are reliable, hardworking and attentive (Andre, 2014, p. 27). They are critic for themselves and others and sure that there is only one right way, feel that they are ethically super, postpone and delay things because they are afraid of doing wrong. Ones can be very clever, moral heroes (Palmer, 1991, p. 37).

Type 2s are the givers and helpers of Enneagram. They have high empathy skills and are often very sociable, friendly and approachable. Once friendships are established, they may lose their boundaries (Andre, 2014, pp.27-28). They want emotional closeness and acceptance. They want to be loved and appreciated as the indispensable person. They dedicate themselves to meeting the needs of others. They are manipulative. They have many personalities, showing a different personality to each good friend. They are seductive (Palmer, 1991, p. 39).

Type 3s are interested in achievement and performance. They are workaholics. They avoid failure. They are friendly and popular. They have an extraordinary ability to mobilize and inspire others. Their intense results-oriented drive often leads to success, but their competitiveness can be destructive for themselves and those close to them (Andre, 2014, p. 28). They want to be loved for their performance and achievements. They are competitive. They are obsessed with appearing winning. They are masters of appearances. They deny their true self and work identity. They try to appear more productive (Palmer, 1991, p. 39).

Type 4s are the most emotional type. They are described as romantic and individualistic. They have excellent creative skills and are highly empathetic, but they are also pensive and dramatic. Many experience melancholy and believe that something is missing from their lives. This leads to self-discovery and intuitive states (Andre, 2017, p. 28). They seek the unattainable. They focus on the tragic, sad, artistic, emotional, absent lover or friend. (Palmer, 1991, p. 39).

Type 5s have private and secretive lives and rarely show their emotions. They focus on knowledge and learning, their fear of inadequacy inhibits their ability to take action. They are known as observers and researchers because they constantly seek knowledge, but they often don't share it. Because of their minimalist approach to life, they isolate themselves from people (Andre, 2014, pp. 28-29). Palmer (1991, p. 39) states that Type 5s keep emotional distance from others, protect their privacy and don't interfere with others. It is a defense for Type 5s to do nothing instead of being involved in something. Attachment and the needs of others make them feel exhausted, so they isolate themselves from people and emotions.

Type 6s have a tendency to be highly analytical, responsible and loyal. They tend to be true to their own beliefs and to their friends. They respond to their inner fears by hiding them or by aggressive ways of challenging their fears. They are called phobic or counter-phobic (Andre, 2014, p. 29). According to Palmer (1991, pp. 39-40) Type 6s are cowardly, responsible, and uncomfortable with doubt. They withdraw and postpone themselves. Thinking takes the place of doing, they are afraid to act. They are described as anti-authoritarian, altruistic and loyal to causes. Phobic 6s are indecisive, feel persecuted and give up when cornered. Counter-phobic 6s feel cornered all the time and therefore tend to fight back more aggressively.

Type 7s have a playful approach to life and are energetic. They can easily lose focus and appear disorganized at times. Taking on too much can lead to procrastination, forgetfulness and even physical exhaustion (Andre, 2014, p. 29). They have a superficial, artificial, adventurous, expecting everything to be good and delicious. They have problems with obedience and want to remain emotionally intense. They are happy most of the time, have a habit of starting things but not seeing them through (Palmer, 1991, p. 40).

Type 8s are bosses or challengers. This type shows a lot of power and force. They have the ability to make things happen through a direct, sometimes coercive approach. Their main fear is to be emotionally hurt. They act confidently, believe in justice, and defend the oppressed (Andre, 2014, pp. 29-30). They are very protective. They defend themselves and their friends, they are aggressive, dominating and love to fight. They should be under control. They can show anger and coercive behaviors, they have great respect for opponents who will stand against them and fight. Evolved 8s are excellent leaders. Type 8 can be strong advocates for others and they want to create an atmosphere of trust for their friends (Palmer, 1991, p. 40).

Type 9s are described as mediators and peacemakers. They hate conflict and they get along well with others because they love peace and harmony. Saying no is difficult for them as it is a personal decision and brings change. They are mostly compliant but at times have strong stubbornness to control others. They are generally cool-headed. They have a calm and reassuring attitude. They get along well with everyone (Andre, 2014, p. 30). They see all points of view. They know the needs of others better than their own needs. They are accepted by others. Evolved 9s are great peacemakers, mediators, counselors, negotiators, and can succeed very well if they are on the right track (Palmer, 1991, pp. 40-41).

1.2.3 Mediation

Conflicts and disagreements are inevitable in all human relationships, societies and cultures, and because of the high cost of conflict, people throughout history have sought peaceful solutions to deal with conflict. Many different effective procedures have been developed to resolve and manage conflicts (Moore, 2014). Conflict resolution is the field of study that encompasses all of the methods used by peacekeepers, family and business interventions, law enforcement and others to find peaceful solutions. Alternative dispute resolution (ADR) is only one part of this field (Beard, 2012, p. 5). Mediation is one of the alternative dispute resolution methods and involves the use of a third party, but unlike an arbitrator or judge, the mediator does not have the authority to impose a solution on

the parties. The purpose of the mediator is to facilitate negotiation and help the parties reach a mutually acceptable resolution of their dispute. It is a private, confidential, non-public, voluntary process (Mnookin, 1998).

In addition to many factors affecting the success of the mediation process, the mediator has a significant impact on conflict resolution and reconciliation (Brett, Drieghe & Shapiro, 1986; Carnevale, 1986; Shapiro, Drieghe, & Brett, 1985; Young, 1972). The mediator's personality, experience and skills affect mediation (Bercovitch & Jackson, 2009, p. 38). Although there are many studies on the methods, models and techniques applied in mediation, there is very little interest and studies on the personality traits of the mediator that will contribute to the process (Collins, 2005, p. 1; Bowling & Hoffman, 2003, p. 14). Wilson and Irvine (2014, pp. 3-5) argue that while there is much caution and polemic about the ideal qualities of mediators, there is very limited empirical work and that personal traits and characteristics have an impact on entry, selection, practice, commercial success and the ability to gain and stay in mediation. When selecting mediators, the personality traits, knowledge and experience of the mediators should be considered (Amar, 2007, pp. 80-81). According to Bowling and Hoffman (2003, pp.13-14) mediation training and learning techniques have a significant contribution to mediation. In addition, the combination of psychological, intellectual and spiritual characteristics of a person also has a significant and direct impact on the mediation process and outcome. According to Moore et al. (2011, p. 77), a mediator must be natural and impartial; give equal voice to the parties; understand the conflict; maintain confidentiality; communicate effectively; ensure trust on all sides; be sensitive to social diversity and understand the subtle imbalance of power in society. Also, a mediator shouldn't be influenced by personal and private values, but should be able to show patience; be honest, mature, empathetic, analytical, and help to negotiate and resolve the dispute. Bowers (2000, ss. 114-115) have also stated that a mediator should be impartial, trustworthy, flexible, creative, patient, able to understand different perspectives, able to analyze problems and discover key points, most importantly able to balance training, knowledge, judgment and intuition and a good listener. Also, researchers state that, building rapport (Crawley & Graham, 2002; Goldberg, 2005), being reliable (Goldberg, 2005; Goldberg, Sander and Rogers, 1992; Monagan & James, 2010; Sandu, 2013; Zaleniene & Tvaronaviciene, 2010), neutral (Astor, 2007; Cloke, 2002; Sandu, 2013; Cooley, 2006; Rahman, 2012; Weinstein, 2001); confidentiality (Meyer, Farrell, Northup, & Plybon, 2000; Murray, 2011; Moore, 2014; Rahman, 2012; Sandu, 2013; Shapira, 2016), optimism (Curtis, 2015; Sandu, 2013; Boulle, Colatrella and Piccighioni, 2008), communication skills (Alikılıç, 2017; Collins, 2005; Meierding, 2004), listening skills (Collins, 2005; Diaz, 2007; Frenkel & Stark, 2018; Meierding, 2004; Rhizome, 2010), empathy (Collins, 2005; Curtis, 2015; Duffy, 2010; Goldberg, 2005; Gordon, 2015; Meierding, 2004; Isenhardt & Spangle, 2000) are very important for a mediator.

2. Method

Structural Equation Modeling was used to examine the mediating role of organizational culture in the relationship between teachers' enneagram personality types and mediation attitudes. Structural equation modeling is a statistical modeling technique seen as a combination of factor analysis, regression and path analysis. It is graphically visualized with a path diagram and the model is presented with a series of matrix equations (Hox & Bechger, 1999, p. 1). Structural equation modeling offers the opportunity to combine and apply multiple regression, factor analysis, (M)ANOVA and many other statistical procedures and is a statistical technique that works with a system of regression equations rather than single or multiple linear regression and takes into account many equations simultaneously (Nachtigall et al., 2003). In the structural equation modeling, Baron and Kenny's (1986) method was used to determine the mediating role. According to Baron and Kenny (1986), there are three stages of modelling. For these models, in this study the independent variable was enneagram personality types, the mediating variable was organizational culture and the dependent variable was mediation attitude.

2.1 Population and Sample

The sample group of the study is 463 teachers working at primary, secondary and high school levels in public schools in Istanbul. Of the 463 teachers who participate in the study, 324 are woman (70%) and 139 are men (30%); 37 (8%) are 21-30 years old, 190 (41%) are 31-40 years old, 163 (35,2%) are 41-50 years old, 73 (15,8%) are aged 51 and over; 365 (78,8%) are married, 98 (21,2%) are single; 102 (22%) have a bachelor degree and 361 (78%) have a master degree; 26 (5,6%) have 0-5 years of service in the teaching profession; 93 (20,1%) have 6-

10 years of service in the teaching profession, 101 (%21,8) have 11-15 years of service in the teaching profession, 75 (%16,2) have 16-20 years of service in the teaching profession and 168 (%36,3) have 21 or more years of service in the teaching profession; 146 (%31,5) work in primary schools, 181 (%39,1) work in middle school and 136 (%29,4) work in high school; 220 (%47,5) have 0-5 years of service in the organization where they work, 132 (%28,5) have 6-10 years of service in the organization where they work, 59 (%12,7) have 11-15 years of service in the organization where they work, 28 (%6) have 16-20 years of service in the organization where they work and 24 (%5,2) have 21 and more years of service in the organization where they work. 62 (%13,4) have 25 or fewer teachers working in their schools, 204 (%44,1) have 26-50 teachers working in their schools and 197 (%42,5) have 51 or more teachers working in their schools.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

"Personal Information Form" created by the researcher, "Enneagram Personality Scale" developed by Subaş and Çetin (2017), "School Culture Scale" developed by Terzi (2005) and "Mediation Attitude Scale" developed by the researcher were used in the study.

2.2.1 Personal Information Form

The personal information form was developed by the researcher and information about the demographic characteristics of the teachers such as gender, age, marital status, educational status, length of service in the teaching profession, type of school, years of service in the school and the number of teachers working in the school were collected.

2.2.2 Enneagram Personality Scale

The Enneagram Personality Scale developed by Subaş and Çetin (2017) is a 4-point Likert-type scale. It has 9 factors with 27 items. Each of the nine Enneagram personality types is included in one factor and each factor has 3 items. Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for the study. According to the results of the CFA analysis, it was seen that the goodness of fit levels of the model were within the acceptable and excellent fit range with $\chi^2/df=1.235$; $RMSEA=0.022$; $SRMR=0.031$, $NFI=0.98$; $CFI=1.00$; $GFI=0.95$ and $AGFI=0.93$ values and it was determined that the factor structure explained was confirmed. In addition, reliability analysis of the dimensions of the scale was conducted and reliability values of the factors were calculated. According to the results of the analysis, Cronbach's Alpha values were 0.827 for Type 1, 0.833 for Type 2, 0.868 for Type 3, 0.805 for Type 4, 0.802 for Type 5, 0.793 for Type 6, 0.839 for Type 7, 0.855 for Type 8, 0.724 for Type 9 and it was determined that the reliability of all factors was high (Cronbach's Alpha>0.70).

2.2.3 School Culture Scale

In the study, the School Culture Scale developed by Terzi (2005) was used. It is a five-point Likert-type scale that includes four factors: support culture, success culture, bureaucratic culture, and task culture, respectively. Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for the study. According to the results of the CFA analysis, it was seen that the goodness of fit levels of the model were within the acceptable and excellent fit range with $\chi^2/df=1.275$; $RMSEA=0.024$; $SRMR=0.032$, $NFI=0.99$; $CFI=0.99$; $GFI=0.93$ and $AGFI=0.92$ values and it was determined that the factor structure explained was confirmed. In addition, reliability analysis of the overall scale was conducted and calculated. According to the results of the analysis, Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.941 for the overall scale so it was determined that the reliability of the overall scale was high (Cronbach's Alpha>0.70).

2.2.4 Mediation Attitude Scale

In the study, Mediation Attitude Scale was developed to measure the mediation attitudes of teachers. It is a five-point Likert-type scale that includes 25 items under four factors which are thought, help and communication, equipment, and behavior respectively. Confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for the study. According to the results of the CFA analysis, it was seen that the goodness of fit levels of the model were within the acceptable and

excellent fit range with $\chi^2/df=4.159$; RMSEA=0.083; SRMR=0.054, NFI=0.96; CFI =0.97; GFI=0.92 and AGFI=0.90 values and it was determined that the factor structure explained was confirmed. In addition, reliability analysis of the overall scale was conducted and calculated. According to the results of the analysis, Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.937 for the overall scale so it was determined that the reliability of the overall scale was high (Cronbach's Alpha>0.70).

2.3 Data Collection

Legal permissions were first obtained to administer the scales. Then, in the first semester of the 2022-2023 academic year, visits were made to schools, teachers were informed about the purpose of the study and what it would be used for and that private information would be kept, the scales were delivered to the volunteer teachers and collected after they answered. A total of 472 forms were collected and incomplete forms were eliminated and a total of 463 data forms were collected.

2.4 Data Analysis

The findings were analyzed with SPSS program and LISREL program. Frequency and percentage analysis was used to determine the distribution of the participants according to their demographic characteristics, and Pearson correlation analysis was used for the relationship between the variables due to the normal distribution of the data. Cronbach's Alpha analysis was used to determine the reliability of the scales, CFA was used to determine the suitability of the factor structures for the study, and structural equation modeling was used to test the mediation model of the study.

3. Results

First of all, the distribution of the data was examined, and as a result of the normal distribution analysis, it was determined that the data obtained from the central tendency measurements examined were from a normal distribution since the mean-median was close to each other and the kurtosis and skewness were between ± 2 (George & Mallery, 2010). Then, the relationships between the measured variables were examined and Pearson correlation results are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Correlations of variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Type 9 (1)	r	1	-0,507	0,587	-0,561	-0,486	-0,523	-0,531	-0,370	0,468	0,466	0,554
	p		0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 3 (2)	r	1		-0,719	0,585	0,698	0,634	0,613	0,482	-0,690	-0,510	-0,541
	p			0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 2 (3)	r		1		-0,549	-0,625	-0,596	-0,494	-0,400	0,620	0,510	0,503
	p				0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 7 (4)	r			1		0,493	0,612	0,506	0,404	-0,626	-0,434	-0,527
	p					0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 1 (5)	r				1		0,575	0,633	0,534	-0,583	-0,483	-0,515
	p						0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 4 (6)	r					1		0,546	0,452	-0,714	-0,493	-0,509
	p							0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 5 (7)	r						1		0,556	-0,616	-0,405	-0,520
	p								0,001*	0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 6 (8)	r							1		-0,488	-0,317	-0,376
	p									0,001*	0,001*	0,001*
Type 8 (9)	r								1		0,509	0,517
	p										0,001*	0,001*
Mediation (10)	r									1		0,546
	p											0,001*
Organizational Culture (11)	r											1
	p											

It was determined that the highest positive correlation was between Type 2, helper personality type and mediation attitudes and that this relationship was significant ($r=0.510$; $p<0.05$). This result means that when mediation levels are improved, helping personality levels will also improve, albeit at a moderate level. Also, it was determined that the highest positive correlation was between Type 9, peace-maker personality type and organizational culture and this relationship was significant ($r=0.554$; $p<0.05$). This result means that when the level of organizational culture is improved, the level of peace-maker personality will also improve, albeit at a moderate level.

It was determined that there was a positive, moderately significant relationship between teachers' mediation attitudes and organizational culture ($r=0.546$; $p<0.05$). This result means that when organizational culture levels are improved, mediation attitude levels will also improve, albeit at a moderate level. The SEM analysis path diagram of the first model established to determine whether teachers' personality types predict mediation attitudes was given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Path diagram for the first model

According to Figure 1, in the first model of the study, the prediction of teachers' personality types on mediation attitudes was examined, and it was determined that the goodness of fit values of the first model of the research were excellent with $\chi^2/df=2.111$, excellent with RMSEA value 0.049, and other fit criteria were in the excellent or acceptable range with CFI: 0.99, NFI: 0.98, NNFI: 0.99, GFI: 0.93, AGFI: 0.91, RMR: 0.048, SRMR: 0.031. The analysis results of the first model are given in Table 2.

Table 2: SEM results for the first model

Paths	Standardized Parameter Estimates	t values	Result
(Type 9)→(Mediation)	0.65	2.54*	Significant
(Type 3)→(Mediation)	-0.21	-0.97	Insignificant
(Type 2)→(Mediation)	-0.30	-1.12	Insignificant
(Type 7)→(Mediation)	0.17	1.28	Insignificant
(Type 1)→(Mediation)	-0.35	-2.09*	Significant
(Type 4)→(Mediation)	0.09	0.45	Insignificant
(Type 5)→(Mediation)	0.38	1.78	Insignificant
(Type 6)→(Mediation)	0.12	1.36	Insignificant
(Type 8)→(Mediation)	0.58	2.33*	Significant

*p<0.05

According to Table 1, it was seen that only Type 9, Type 1 and Type 8 personality types significantly predicted teachers' mediation attitudes ($t > 1.96$; $p < 0.05$). With this result, it was determined that Type 9 personality type had a positive effect of 0.65 units, Type 8 personality type had a positive effect of 0.58 units, and Type 1 personality type had a negative effect of 0.35 units on teachers' mediation attitudes.

In the second model of the study, only Type 1, Type 8 and Type 9 were used among the personality types that had a significant effect on the dependent variable. In the second model of the study, the SEM analysis path diagram of the model related to the prediction of personality types on organizational culture and organizational culture on teachers' mediation attitudes is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Path diagram of the second model

According to Figure 2, the goodness of fit values of the model were acceptable with $X^2/sd=3.983$, RMSEA value was acceptable with 0.092, and other fit criteria were found to be in the excellent or acceptable range with CFI: 0.99, NFI: 0.98, NNFI: 0.98, GFI: 0.92, AGFI: 0.90, RMR: 0.013, SRMR: 0.010. The results of the second model of the study are given in Table 3.

Table 3: SEM results for the second model

Paths	Standardized Parameter Estimates	t values
(Type 9)→(O. C.)	0,54	6,70*
(Type 1)→(O. C.)	-0,19	-2.34*
(Type 8)→(O. C)	0,23	3.19*
(O. C.)→(Mediation)	0,82	12.18*

*p<0.05

When Table 3 is examined; the prediction of organizational culture by personality types was found statistically significant for Type 9 ($t=6.70 > 1.96$ $p < 0.05$), Type 1 ($t=-2.34 > -1.96$; $p < 0.05$) and Type 8 ($t=3.19 > 1.96$ $p < 0.05$). These results show that teachers' Type 9 personality type has a positive effect of 0.54 on organizational culture, Type 8 personality type has a positive effect of 0.23 on organizational culture and Type 1 personality type has a negative effect of 0.19 units on organizational culture.

Also, that organizational culture predicts teachers' mediation attitudes, was found to be statistically significant ($t=12.18 > 1.96$ $p < 0.05$). This result indicates that a one-unit increase in the participants' organizational culture levels will lead to a 0.82-unit increase in their mediation attitude levels.

The results of the last model (Model 3), which decides whether there is mediation or not, are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Path diagram for mediating role

According to Figure 3, the goodness of fit values of the established model were acceptable with $\chi^2/df=3.967$, RMSEA value was acceptable with 0.090, and other fit criteria were determined to be in the excellent or acceptable range with CFI: 0.99, NFI: 0.99, NNFI: 0.99, GFI: 0.93, AGFI: 0.90, RMR: 0.022, SRMR: 0.015. The results of the mediating role of the research are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Effect coefficients for the mediating role of the study

Paths	Impact Coefficients			Result
	Standardized β	t	p	
Type 9 → Med.	0.13	1.35	P>0.05	Full Mediation
Type 1 → Med.	-0.12	-1.42	P>0.05	Full Mediation
Type 8 → Med.	0.23	3.08*	P<0.05	Partial Mediation

*p<0.05

When Figure 3 and Table 4 are examined, it is determined that the effect path of organizational culture on mediation has an effect of 0.41 and is significant at 99% confidence level. Since this condition is met, mediation can be examined according to Baron and Kenny. To talk about mediation according to Baron and Kenny, the first model in which the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable without the mediating variable is given should be examined. According to the first model it was determined that the effect of Type 9 on mediation in was 0.65, Type 1 was -0.35 and Type 8 was 0.58 and these paths were significant. When the final model was examined as a result of the inclusion of the mediator variable in the model, it was determined that the effect of Type 9 on mediation was 0.13 ($t=1.35 < 1.96$; $p > 0.05$), and the effect of Type 1 on mediation was -0.12 ($t=-1.42 < 1.96$; $p > 0.05$) was found to be insignificant so it was determined that organizational culture was a full mediator, and the effect of Type 8 on mediation was found to be significant at 0.23 ($t=3.08 > 1.96$ $p < 0.05$), but it was determined to be partially mediated because it reduced its effect from 0.58 to 0.23 when there was no mediator variable.

4. Discussion

In this study, the relationships between teachers' enneagram personality types, their perceived organizational culture and mediation attitudes were examined. When the literature was reviewed, no study about examining directly the relationship between teachers' enneagram personality types, mediation and organizational culture was found. Therefore, the results were discussed by utilizing similar topics and samples.

According to the results of the correlation analysis, the highest positive relationship between enneagram personality types and mediation attitudes was found between Type 2 and mediation attitudes. Similarly, Şahin (2019, p. 96) found out that Type 2 preferred the integration method in his study. Integration is a win-win style of conflict resolution in which the needs of both parties are taken into account, just like mediation, and problem solving is done in cooperation (Rahim, 2023, p. 29). This result supports the research.

Also, the highest positive relationship between Enneagram personality types and organizational culture was found between Type 9 and organizational culture. Type 9 is the type that does not like conflict in organizations, likes harmony, and wants to work in harmony (McPartlin, 2021; Palmer, 1995). Therefore, this type can be expected to have a high perception of organizational culture. The research also supports this. In addition, a positive and moderately significant relationship was found between mediation attitude and organizational culture. Similarly, Özkara and Tunç (2020) found a positive relationship between organizational culture and integration as a conflict method.

According to the first model of the structural equation model, only three of the personality types of the teachers predicted the mediation attitudes. According to the results of the analysis, among the personality types of the teachers, Type 9 and Type 8 have a significant positive effect on mediation attitudes while Type 1 has a significant negative effect. For Type 8s, this may be due to the fact that Type 8s protect the powerless, try to help them and provide justice (Andre, 2014; Palmer, 1991; Palmer, 1995; Riso & Hudson, 2003). Because Type 8s are the people who express the unhappiness of people who are unhappy but do not express it (Palmer, 1995, p. 219). For Type 9s, the result may be due to the fact that this personality type attaches importance to peace and togetherness, calms people down and tries to help the environment to prosper (Riso & Hudson, 2003, pp. 164-165) and because Type 9s love peace, approach impartially, look for alternative ways and try to ensure peace (Palmer, 1995, pp. 224-236). Yılmaz, et al. (2016), who examined the relationship between personality types in the conceptually similar five-

factor personality theory and enneagram personality types, found a strong positive relationship between Type 1 personality type and conscientiousness, Type 9 personality type and agreeableness, and Type 8 personality type and extraversion. Considering this situation, it was seen that similar results were reached for Type 9 and Type 8 in studies examining conflict management and five-factor personality types (Forrester & Tashchian, 2013; Yürür, 2009; Yıldızoğlu & Burgaz, 2014; Turhan & Tiftik, 2022).

The reason for the result in the Type 1 may be that Type 1s feel that it is not their responsibility to help others in a dispute and that they will be disempowered if they support someone in a dispute (Palmer, 1995, p. 57). Therefore, it may seem usual for Type 1s to prefer to avoid mediation. Şahin (2019) concluded that Type 1s chose dominance method as the first choice quite often. Since the dominance method can be considered as the opposite of mediation, this result supports the findings of this study. In the light of these studies, it can be said that Type 1s withdraws themselves from mediation in case of a dispute and Type 1 has a negative effect on the mediation attitude of the person.

Among the personality types of teachers, Type 9, Type 8 and Type 1 significantly predict organizational culture. According to the results of the analysis, Type 9 and Type 8 have a positive effect on organizational culture, while Type 1 has a negative effect. Type 9s like to take part in organizations, care about the needs of others and tend to get together with them (Sutton, 2007). This type gets along well with everyone, gives confidence, is harmonious and takes on the role of peacemaker and mediator when there is a problem (Andre, 2014). Therefore, it can be considered normal for Type 9s to have the understanding of organizational culture in order to gain a sense of belonging and to keep the organization alive, to spread it within the organization and to try to keep the organization alive. All these may have enabled Type 9s to have a positive impact on organizational culture.

Type 8s are the types who value rules in organizations, have leadership potential, and at the same time are very protective and want to create an environment of trust that defends their friends (Palmer, 1991; 1995). In addition, this type with leadership characteristics can show themselves at the highest level in assertive and defensive organizations (McPartlin, 2021). Therefore, they can be popular and desired people within organizations. In addition, this defensive and leadership trait may have had a positive impact on organizational culture.

Type 1s want everything to be the best and the most accurate and they give importance to plans, programs, details and prefer to be formal with everyone (Palmer, 1995). Because they dedicate themselves to perfection and do not like others in their work, they isolate themselves (Riso & Hudson, 2003). In addition, according to Palmer (1995), Type 1s do not blame themselves when mistakes are made. All these may cause them not to feel belonging in organizations and not to be liked by the members of the organization. Therefore, it may be possible for this type to negatively affect the organizational culture. Hebenstreit (2008) found out in his study that Type 9s attach more importance to collaborative work environment and Type 1s want a more competitive and skill-oriented salary system. In other words, Type 9s attach more importance to the organization and organizational culture, while Type 1s attach more importance to their own skills and the reward and salary they will receive. This result supports the conclusion reached in this study.

Teachers' level of organizational culture significantly predicts their mediation attitudes. According to the results of the analysis, an increase in organizational culture leads to an increase in teachers' mediation attitudes. In the literature, there are studies showing positive relationships between organizational culture and organizational commitment (Erkmen & Bozkurt, 2011; Singh, 2007). In a place where there is organizational commitment, teachers can mediate when there is a conflict. There are also studies that the prevailing organizational culture affects the method to be chosen in case of conflict (Kaushal & Kwantes, 2006; Özarallı, 2015; Özkara & Tunç, 2020; Veerankutty & Rehna, 2020). Therefore, if mediation is desired in schools, the impact of organizational culture on people's mediation attitudes should not be ignored. The importance of organizational culture should be taken into account, as people's commitment and sense of belonging to their institution will also affect their mediation attitudes.

Organizational culture has a mediating role in the relationship between Type 9, Type 8 and Type 1 personality types and mediation attitudes. Here, organizational culture is a full mediator in Type 9 and Type 1, while

organizational culture is a partial mediator in Type 8. Type 9s are people who like to take part in the organization and attach importance to cooperation (Sutton, 2007). Therefore, it can be seen as usual that organizational culture is a full mediator. Type 1s may isolate themselves by holding themselves responsible for doing the job because they think that others cannot do it as perfectly as they do (Riso & Hudson, 2003, pp. 90-91). On the other hand, they are people who maintain their formality in organizations, attach importance to plans and programs, and respect authority (Palmer, 1995). Therefore, high efficiency can be obtained if they are welcomed in the same way in their organizations (McPartlin, 2021, p. 107). Therefore, depending on the perceptions of organizational culture, it can be seen as usual that the organizational culture is a full mediator. In this context, if it is desired to increase the mediation attitudes of personality types, it is important to create a strong and effective organizational culture that will enable personality types to experience satisfaction and use their potential at the maximum level. In the literature, there are studies that cannot fully explain the conflict management styles of personality types and it is thought that variables such as culture may affect the collaborative conflict management style (Erkuş & Tabak, 2009). In this study, in addition to the effect of personality types on mediation attitude, it was concluded that organizational culture also has a mediating effect. Type 8, on the other hand, are people who already have high leadership qualities, who attach importance to ensuring justice and defending the weak (Andre, 2014). Therefore, the partial mediation of organizational culture can be considered normal.

In the literature, there are studies examining the relationship between personality types and conflict resolution methods and concluding that different personality types are associated with different conflict resolution methods (Rahaman et al., 2010; Antonioni, 1998; Tuna & Türkmen, 2015; Yürür, 2009; Yıldızoğlu & Burgaz, 2014; Turhan & Tiftik, 2022). However, trainings on conflict management are ineffective because they ignore the impact of personality. In fact, when a person understands the relationship between personality and conflict resolution, he/she will gain self-awareness, adjust his/her behavior, and learn behaviors that will provide reconciliation (Rahaman et al., 2010, pp. 21-22). In addition, there are studies showing that there is a relationship between organizational culture and integration style, which is one of the conflict solutions and has a similar logic with mediation, which is an alternative solution method (Bağdatlı, 2015; Özkara & Tunç, 2020). Also, Erkuş & Tabak (2009) stated that factors such as organizational culture other than personality may be effective in collaborative conflict management. Therefore, when personality types, organizational culture and mediation are considered together, personality types will have an impact on the person's perspective on the conflict, his/her progress in managing the conflict and getting results, as well as the culture of the organization he/she is in will have an impact on his/her attitude in this mediation. Therefore, in addition to being guided to mediate by knowing the personality types of people, the culture of the organization should also be in a structure that supports mediation in the background and it should enable people to be and live in their healthy personality types, in which they can fully reflect their personality types and realize themselves.

In an age when alternative conflict resolution approaches have increased and become widespread, mediation should be further researched and contributed to the literature. Therefore, more research should be conducted on mediation in work environments with organizational structure. It has been observed that personality types and organizational culture are effective for people to become mediators. In addition, other factors that may be effective in mediation can be investigated. In another study, the sub-dimensions of organizational culture on mediation can also be investigated.

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References

- Aktürk, Z., & Taştan, K. (2020). Frequency of personality types based on enneagram in a Turkish sample: A web-based cross-sectional study. *Ortadoğu Tıp Dergisi*, 12(2), 211-218. <https://doi.org/10.21601/ortadogutipdergisi.722751>
- Alikılıç, Ö. (2017). *Arabuluculukta etkili iletişim/ Arabuluculukta etkili yöntemler ve iletişim yönetimi [Effective communication in mediation / Effective methods and communication management in mediation]*. Ankara: Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık.
- Amar, D. D. (2007). *The labor and employment lawyer's job: A survival guide*. American Bar Association.
- Andre, S. (2014). *Reliability and validation study of the online instinctual variant questionnaire*. (Unpublished doctoral thesis). Florida Atlantic University, The Faculty of The College of Education, U.S.
- Antonioni, D. (1998). Relationship between the big five personality factors and conflict management styles. *International journal of conflict management*, 9(4), 336-355.
- Arpağuş, A. U. (2011). *Okul kültürünün öğretmen davranışlarına etkisi [The effect of school culture on teacher behaviors]* (Master's thesis). Trakya Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Edirne.
- Astor, H. (2007). Mediator neutrality: Making sense of theory and practice. *Social & Legal Studies*, 16(2), 221-239. doi: 10.1177/0964663907076531
- Ayık, A. & Ada, Ş. (2009). İlköğretim okullarında oluşturulan okul kültürü ile okulların etkililiği arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between school culture and school effectiveness in primary schools]. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 8(2), 429-446.
- Bağdatlı, F. (2015). *Okul yöneticilerinin çatışma yönetimi stilleri ile örgüt kültürü arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between school administrators' conflict management styles and organizational culture]* (Master's thesis). İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Baron, R.M., & Kenny, D.A. (1986). The Moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51 (6), 1173- 1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- Beard, G. (2012). *Everything you need to know about mediation*. BrainMass Ebook.
- Bercovitch, J., & Jackson, R. . (2009). *Conflict resolution in the twenty-first century: principles, methods, and approaches*. University of Michigan Press.
- Boulle, L. J., Colatrella, M. T. Jr., & Picchioni, A. P. (2008). *Mediation: skills and techniques*. Lexis Nexis Matthew Bender.
- Bowers, (2000). The rural mediation service. Marian Liebmann (Ed.), *Mediation in context* içinde (ss.96-111). London: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Bowling, D., & Hoffman, D. (2003). Bringing peace into the room: The personal qualities of the mediator and their impact on the mediation. Bowling, D. ve Hoffman, D. (Eds.) *Bringing peace into the room: The personal qualities of the mediator and their impact on the mediation* içinde (ss13-49.) John Wiley & Sons.
- Brett, J. M., Drieghe, R., & Shapiro, D. L. (1986). Mediator style and mediation effectiveness. *Negotiation Journal*, 2(3), 277-285. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1571-9979.1986.tb00365.x>
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2006). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework*. San Francisco, C A.: John Wiley & Sons.
- Carnevale, P. J. (1986). Strategic choice in mediation. *Negotiation Journal*, 2(1), 41-56.
- Cloke, K. (2002). *Mediating dangerously: The frontiers of conflict resolution*. San Francisco, C A.: John Wiley & Sons.
- Collins, H. (2005). The most important personal qualities a mediator needs. https://icfml.files.wordpress.com/2014/11/the20mostimportantpersonalqualitiesamediatorneeds_collins2005.pdf
- Cooley, J. W. (2006). *The mediator's handbook: Advanced practice guide for civil litigation*. USA: National Institute for Trial Advocacy.
- Crawley, J, & Graham, K. (2002). *Mediation for managers: Resolving conflict and rebuilding relationships at work* (1st edition). London: Nicholas Brealey Publishing
- Curtis, D. (2015). Chapter 24 mediation and care management. Cress, C. (Ed.), *Handbook of geriatric care management* içinde (ss. 511-541). Burlington, MA: Jones & Bartlett Publishers.
- Dağlı, B. (2013). *Liderin çatışma yönetiminde arabuluculuk rolü [The mediation role of the leader in conflict management]* (Master's thesis). Kara Harp Okulu Komutanlığı, Savunma Bilimleri Enstitüsü.
- Deal, T. E., & Peterson, K. D. (2016). *Shaping school culture*. San Francisco, C.A.: Jossey-Bass.
- Demirtaş, Z. (2010). Liselerde okul kültürü ile öğrenci başarısı arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between school culture and student achievement in high schools]. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 7(13), 208-223.
- Denison, D. R., & Spreitzer, G. M. (1991). Organizational culture and organizational development: A competing values approach. *Research in organizational change and development*, 5(1), 1-21.

- Diaz, R. (2007). Ten keys to successful mediation. <https://www.diazmediation.com/user/V2%20Ten%20Keys%20to%20Successful%20Mediation.pdf>
- Duffy, J. (2010). Empathy, neutrality and emotional intelligence: A balancing act for the emotional Einstein. *Queensland U. Tech. L. & Just. J.*, 10, 44.
- Erkmen, T., & Bozkurt, S. (2011). Örgüt kültürü ve örgütsel bağlılık ilişkisinin incelenmesine yönelik bir araştırma [A research on the relationship between organizational culture and organizational commitment]. *Marmara Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 31(2), 197-227.
- Erkuş, A., & Tabak, A. (2010). Beş faktör kişilik özelliklerinin çalışanların çatışma yönetim tarzlarına etkisi: savunma sanayisinde bir araştırma [the effect of five factor personality traits on employees' conflict management styles: a research in defense industry]. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 23(2), 213-242.
- Ferda, F., & Karabulut, Y. (2004). Sunuş. İçinde D. N. Daniels ve Price V. A. *Enneagram Kendini Bilme Sanatı [Presentation, The Enneagram The Art of Self-Knowledge]*. Seda Çiftçi (Çev.) (s.7-8). İstanbul: Kaknüs Yayınları
- Forrester, W. R., & Tashchian, A. (2013). Effects of personality on conflict resolution in student teams: A structural equation modeling approach. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning (TLC)*, 10(1), 39-46. <https://doi.org/10.19030/tlc.v10i1.7529>
- Frenkel, D. N., & Stark, J. H. (2018). *The practice of mediation: A video-integrated text*. New York: Aspen Publishers.
- Garner, E. (2012). *Understanding personality types: Managing people through their personality traits*. Ventus Publishing. [www.bookboon.com](http://bookboon.com/en/understanding-personality-types-ebook). <http://bookboon.com/en/understanding-personality-types-ebook>.
- George, D., & Mallery, M. (2010). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference, 17.0 update (10a ed.)*. Boston: Pearson.
- Goldberg, S. B. (2005). The secrets of successful mediators. *Negotiation Journal*, 21(3), 365-376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1571-9979.2005.00069.x>
- Goldberg, S. B., Sander, F. E. A., & Rogers, N.H. (1992). *Dispute resolution: Negotiations, mediation and other processes*. London: Little, Brown and Company.
- Gordon, J. (2015). Empathy in mediation listening between the lines. GordonADR, LLC. <https://www.gordonadr.com/Artwork/Empathy%20in%20Mediation.pdf>
- Gruenert, S., & Whitaker, T. (2015). *School culture rewired: How to define, assess, and transform it*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.
- Güloğlu, F. (2011). *Çatışan öğrenciler ile arabulucu öğrencilerin "akran arabuluculuk" uygulamalarına ilişkin görüşlerinin incelenmesi [Examining the views of conflicted students and mediator students on "peer mediation" practices]* (Master's thesis). Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir.
- Handy, C. B. (1976). *Understanding organizations*. Penguin Books.
- Harrison, R. (1972). Organization's character. *Harvard Business Review*, ss. 119-128.
- Hebenstreit, R. P. (2008). A call to apply the principles of the enneagram in organizations to attract, retain and motivate employees. *Enneagram Journal*, 1(1), 4-21.
- Himmetoğlu, B. (2014). *İlkokullardaki öğretmen görüşlerine göre okul kültürü ile yöneticilerin çatışma yönetimi stilleri arasındaki ilişkilerin değerlendirilmesi [Evaluation of the relationship between school culture and administrators' conflict management styles according to primary school teachers' views]*(Master thesis). Anadolu Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eskişehir.
- Hox, J. J. ve Bechger, T. M. (1999). An introduction to structural equation modeling. *Family Science Review*, 11, 354-373
- Isenhardt, M. W., & Spangle, M. L. (2000). *Collaborative approaches to resolving conflict*. Sage.
- Kaya, Ö. Y. (2015). *Örgüt kültürü ve örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışı ilişkisi (Balıkesir ili merkez ilçe örneği) [The relationship between organizational culture and organizational citizenship behavior (The case of central district of Balıkesir province)]*(Master thesis). Balıkesir Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Balıkesir.
- Kaushal, R., & Kwantes, C. T. (2006). The role of culture and personality in choice of conflict management strategy. *International journal of intercultural relations*, 30(5), 579-603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2006.01.001>
- Kruse, S. D., & Louis, K. S. (2008). *Building strong school cultures: A guide to leading change*. Corwin Press.
- Le Clear, E. A. (2005). *Relationships among leadership styles, school culture, and student achievement*. (Unpublished doctoral thesis). University of Florida, USA.
- Magnuson, K. J. (2011). *How personality types have an effect on work team conflicts and conflict management* (Doctoral thesis). The College of St. Scholastica, Duluth, MN.
- Makani, H. K. (2010). *The Enneagram: Your personal path of growth*. Forlaget Akasha
- McPartlin, J. (2021). *The enneagram at work: Unlocking the power of type to lead and succeed*. St. Martin's Publishing Group.

- Meierding, N. R. (2004). Chapter 11 Managing the communication process in mediation. Jay Folberg, Ann Milne, Peter Salem (Eds.), *Divorce and family mediation: Models, techniques, and applications* içinde (ss.225-247). New York: Guilford Press.
- Meyer, A. L., Farrell, A., Northup, W., Kung, E., & Plybon, L. (2000). *Promoting non-violence in early adolescence: Responding in peaceful and positive ways*. New York: Springer Science & Business Media.
- Miles, R. E., & Snow, C. C. (2003). *Organizational strategy, structure, and process*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press.
- Mnookin, R. (1998). Alternative dispute resolution. *Harvard Law School John M. Olin Center for Law, Economics and Business Discussion Paper Series*, Paper 232.
- Monagan, S. ve James, E. (2010). *Problem solving mediation training: Facilitator's guide*. Lulu. com.
- Moore, C. W. (2014). *The mediation process: Practical strategies for resolving conflict*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Moore, C. W., Jayasundere, R., & Thirunavukarasu, M. (2011). *Mediation process trainee's manual community mediation programme*. Community Mediation Program, Sri Lanka Ministry of Sri Lanka.
- Murray, O. R. (2011). *The mediation handbook*. Denver, Colorado: Bradford Publishing Company.
- Nachtigall, C., Kroehne, U., Funke, F. & Steyer, R. (2003). Why should we use SEM? Pros and cons of structural equation modeling. *Methods Psychological Research Online*, 8(2), 1-22.
- Özaralli, N. (2015). Örgüt kültürü ve işe ilişkin duygusal iyilik algısının çalışanların çatışma çözümü tarzları üzerindeki etkisi [The effect of organizational culture and perception of emotional well-being on employees' conflict resolution styles.]. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(2), 7-37.
- Özkara, E., & Tunç, B. (2020). Okul yöneticilerinin çatışma yönetim stratejileri ile okul kültürü arasındaki ilişkinin öğretmen görüşlerine göre incelenmesi [Examining the relationship between school administrators' conflict management strategies and school culture according to teachers' views.]. *Journal of Faculty of Educational Sciences*, 53(3), 1023 - 1050. DOI:10.30964/auebfd.693129
- Özmen, F., & Aküzüm, C. (2010). Okulların kültürel yapısı içinde çatışmalara bakış açısı ve çatışma çözümünde okul yöneticilerinin liderlik davranışları [The perspective of conflicts in the cultural structure of schools and leadership behaviors of school administrators in conflict resolution.]. *Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Dergisi*, 2(2), 78-83.
- Palmer, H. (1991). *The Enneagram: Understanding yourself and the others in your life*. New York: HarperSanFrancisco, A Division of HarperCollins.
- Palmer, H. (1995). *The Enneagram in love and work: Understanding your intimate and business relationships*. New York: HarperCollins.
- Pheysey, D. C. (2003). *Organizational cultures: Types and transformations*. Routledge.
- Rahaman, H. M. S., Mollah, M. S. ve Uddin, M. K. (2010). Big five personality factors and conflict handling styles. *Dhaka University Journal of Management*, 2(1), 13-24.
- Rahim, M. A. (2023). *Managing conflict in organizations*. Routledge Taylor & Francis.
- Rahman, K. A. (2012). Mediation and mediator skills: A critical appraisal. *Bangladesh Research Foundation Journal*, 1(1), 223-232.
- Renihan, P. J., Phillips, S., & Raham, H. (2006). *The role of the school principal: Present status and future challenges in managing effective schools* (Vol. 25). SAEF.
- Rhizome (2010). *Rhizome guide to Active Listening in Mediation*. https://rhizomenetwork.files.wordpress.com/2010/12/active_listening_in_mediation.pdf
- Riso, D. R., & Hudson, R. (2003). *Discovering your personality type: The essential introduction to the Enneagram*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Sandu, C. (2013). Mediation. Measuring the success of mediation. *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, 2, 30-39.
- Sarı, R. K., & Helvacı, M. A. (2019). Okulların örgüt kültürü ile değişime hazırbulunuşluk düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Examining the relationship between organizational culture and readiness for change in schools]. *Kırıkkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(2), 307-320.
- Schein, E. H. (2004). *Organizational culture and leadership* (3rd Edition). San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.
- Schewee III, W. A. (2023). *Examining Personality Traits of Teachers Utilizing the Enneagram* (Doctoral thesis). Dallas Baptist University.
- Shapira, O. (2016). *A theory of Mediators' ethics. Foundations, rationale, and application*. U.K.: Cambridge University Press.
- Shapiro, D. L., Drieghe, R., & Brett, J. M. (1985). Mediator behavior and the outcome of mediation. *Journal of Social Issues*, 41(2), 101-114. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.1985.tb00857.x>
- Singh, K. (2007). Predicting organizational commitment through organization culture: A study of automobile industry in India. *Journal of business economics and management*, 8(1), 29-37.
- Subaş, A. (2017). *Okul yöneticilerinin "liderlik stilleri" ile "enneagram kişilik tipleri" arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi [Investigating the relationship between school principals' "leadership styles" and "enneagram personality types"]*. (Doctoral thesis). Marmara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul.

- Subaş, A., & Çetin, M. (2017). Güvenirlik ve geçerlilik çalışması. *Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi (SOBİDER)*, 4(11), 160-181.
- Sucuoğlu, E. (2015). Devlet lisesi öğretmenlerinin çatışma nedenleri ve çatışma yönetimi yaklaşımlarının değerlendirilmesi [Evaluation of conflict causes and conflict management approaches of public high school teachers]. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi (H. U. Journal of Education)*, 30(4), 16-28.
- Sutton, A. (2007). *Implicit and explicit personality in work settings: An application of Enneagram theory* (Doctoral thesis). University of Leeds.
- Şahin, A. (2019). *Conflict management for retail store project development process: Personality perspective* (Master thesis). İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul
- Şener C. (2006). *Ankara ili Keçiören ilçesindeki kamu liselerinde görev yapan öğretmenlerin arabuluculuk yoluyla çatışma çözme davranışları [Conflict resolution behaviors of teachers working in public high schools in Keçiören district of Ankara province through mediation]* (Master thesis). Ankara Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Terzi, A. R. (2005). İlköğretim okullarında örgüt kültürü [Organizational culture in primary schools]. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 43(43), 423-442.
- Tuna, M., & Türkmen, F. (2015). Kişilik tiplerinin çatışmayı yönetme yöntemlerine etkisi [The effect of personality types on conflict management methods]. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(4), 43-65.
- Turan, S., & Taylor, C., (1997). Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR): A different framework for conflict resolution in educational settings. *National Council of Professors of Educational Administration's (NCPEA) 51st Annual Conference* içinde. Colorado, USA. chrome- <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED423206.pdf>
- Turhan, Ö., & Tiftik, C. (2022). Beş Faktör kişilik özelliklerinin çatışma yönetme stratejilerine etkisi [The effect of Five Factor personality traits on conflict management strategies]. *IBAD Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, (12), 181-210. 10.21733/ibad.955563
- Veerankutty, K. & Rehna, V. J. (2020). Role of organizational culture in resolving organizational conflict and its impact on employees performance—A critical overview. *International Journal of Innovations in Management, Engineering and Science (IJIMES)*, 6 (3), 1-8.
- Victorian Association for Dispute Resolution (VADR). (2001). *Mediation in schools*. http://www.vadr.asn.au/mediation_in_schools.pdf
- Yaraş, Z., & Gündüzalp, S. (2021). Regarding the school administrators' conflict resolution strategies about organizational conflicts: An assessment according to teacher opinions. *International Journal of Education Technology and Scientific Researches*, 6(14), 397-430. <http://dx.doi.org/10.35826/ijetsar.194>
- Yıldızoğlu, H., & Burgaz, B. (2014). Okul yöneticilerinin beş faktör kişilik özellikleriyle çatışma yönetimi stili tercihleri arasındaki ilişki [The relationship between school administrators' five factor personality traits and conflict management style preferences]. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 29(2), 295-310.
- Yılmaz, E., Ünal, Ö., Palancı, M., Gençer, A., Örek, A., Tatar, A., ..., & Aydemir, Ö. (2016). The relation between the nine types temperament model and the five factor personality model in a Turkish sample group. *British Journal of Medicine and Medical Research*, 11(4), 1-11. DOI: 10.9734/BJMMR/2016/20303
- Young, O. R. (1972). Intermediaries: Additional thoughts on third parties. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 51-65.
- Yürür, S. (2009). Yöneticilerin çatışma yönetim tarzları ve kişilik özellikleri arasındaki ilişkinin analizine yönelik bir araştırma [A study to analyze the relationship between managers' conflict management styles and personality traits]. *Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 10(1), 23-42.
- Weinstein, R. J. (2001). *Mediation in the workplace: A guide for training, practice, and administration*. Greenwood Publishing Group.
- Wilson, B., & Irvine, C. (2014). What do we know about mediators? A short literature review. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2510786>
- Zaleniene, I., & Tvaronaviciene A. (2010). The main features and development trends of mediation in Lithuania: the opportunities for lawyers. *Jurisprudencija*, 119(1), 227-242.
- Zembat, R. (2012). Okul öncesi öğretmenlerinin okul yöneticisi, meslektaşları ve aileler bağlamında algıladıkları çatışma durumlarının incelenmesi [Examining the conflict situations perceived by preschool teachers in the context of school administrators, colleagues and parents]. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 37(163), 203-215.